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FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

SMILE NEWS RELEASE N° 3

Supporting Mental health in young People: Integrated Methodology for cLinical dEcisions and evidence-based interventions

Image: The South Entrance of the Cologne Exhibition Center at the time of Gamescom 2023. Image by [Diskusfisch](#). CC BY-SA 4.0.

www.horizonmile.eu

SMILE Announces Participation at Gamescom 2024

Les Mureaux, France, August 01, 2024, **SMILE**, a collaborative project, funded under Horizon Europe Programme, is set to tackle the rising issue of youth mental health by developing digital solutions to empower young people aged 10 to 24. SMILE's unique approach combines gaming, technology, and expert research to create engaging and effective mental health support tools for young people.

The project announces its participation at **Gamescom 2024** in Cologne, Germany, from August 21st to 25th, 2024, to showcase **SMILE Youth Mental Health Solutions** at the world's largest trade fair for video games and interactive entertainment. SMILE has a unique opportunity to reach a vast audience of young people and network with potential business partners for project development and impact.

SMILE Partner, Nurogames, a fast-growing technology company, with over 18 years of experience in the gaming industry, will host a booth where visitors will have the exclusive opportunity to learn about the latest developments in SMILE serious game – a game designed to help young people develop coping mechanisms and build resilience.

Dr. Dominic Heutelbeck, CEO of FTK and SMILE Project Coordinator, states: "We are thrilled to present our approach to helping adolescents cope with the modern world's mental health challenges. Gamescom is an ideal event to reach out to our target audience and engage with them by presenting the first version of our game. We look forward to feedback from young gamers, their guardians, and potential healthcare professionals who are interested in our solutions."

Representatives from SMILE including **Nurogames, FTK, Heriott-Watt University, University of Maribor, and Heidelberg University Hospital** will be present at the booth, leveraging diverse expertise to provide a comprehensive overview of the project.

Join us at Gamescom 2024: We invite you to visit the SMILE booth at Gamescom 2024 and experience firsthand the project's innovative approach to youth mental health. Stay tuned for further details about the booth location and line-up of activities.

Meet the SMILE team there:

- Location: Cologne, Germany
- Venue: Koelnmesse
- Dates: August 21st to 25th, 2024
- Hall & Stand: Information to be confirmed soon

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Media are welcome to contact us for interview opportunities or further information.